

LIFESTYLES AND HERNIATION OF THE CERVIX

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Relevance: At present, in connection with the development of technology and the improvement of living conditions, the lifestyle of people of the current generation is also progressively changing, which contributes to people leading a passive lifestyle. As a result of abundant vascularization and structural features of the cervical spine, this pathology exhibits various clinical signs depending on the location. In this case, symptoms are characteristic, such as the appearance of pain in the cervical region, with irradiation to the upper limbs and the back of the head, numbness and physical inactivity of the hands. The frequency of hernia in this area is 16%, which is much more prevalent compared to thoracic hernia (1%), which is explained by the peculiarity of the anatomical structure of the cervical spine. The absence of early clinical signs, timely diagnosis and the use of mainly conservative methods of treatment by different specialists, leading to aggravation of the patient's condition and the appearance of neurological deficits among the socially active population aged 30 to 60 years, indicates the relevance of this problem.

Purpose of the study: The purpose of this work is to analyze the theory of the formation of deformation processes in the vertebrae and their connection with the way of life of patients.

Materials and methods: The study used clinical data of 40 patients of the neurology department of the 1st clinic of the Samara State Medical University, with the above complaints. The study of changes in the state of the intervertebral discs was carried out using CT and MRI studies, with different sections.

Results and discussions: Most of the examined patients, in whom the MRI study revealed: 21 (55%) protrusion of the intervertebral disc, 11 (27.5%) with deformity of the spinal column in the neck, 8 (20%) with herniated disc. According to the anamnesis: 11 (27.5%) patients were drivers by profession who had been engaged in this activity for more than 5 years, 9 (22.5%) were engaged in banking activities, 13 (32.5%) were programmers who spend at least 8 hours per day at the computer, 7 (17.5%) dentists who work motionless in one position, 2 (5%) students of the medical institute.

Conclusion: According to the following data, it can be concluded that pathologies of the spinal column are found mainly in people with a sedentary lifestyle, holding an incorrect posture during the day, not exercising, leading an incorrect daily routine and violations of natural metabolic processes in the structures of the vertebrae. Due to the fact that the frequency of occurrence in professional workers, who are relatively higher in working age, should follow a correct lifestyle, combine mental and physical labor, wear cervical collars if necessary and receive physiotherapy, with the use of foods rich in vitamins and minerals, which significantly reduce the risk of developing deformities and diseases of the spine.

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